

LINGUOCULTURAL PROPERTIES OF WORDS IN THE STUDIED LANGUAGES

Sh.Halikova

TITLI, independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14524680>

Annotation

The article discusses issues of language learning. It is emphasized that cultural linguistics is oriented towards a new system of cultural values put forward by new thinking, modern life of society, a complete, objective interpretation of facts and phenomena and information about various areas of the cultural life of the country.

Keywords: linguistic culture, language, semiotics. image, symbol, system, the formation of a fact, a form of society, information.

The development of the cultural linguistics direction is determined by the desire to understand the phenomenon of culture as a specific form of human existence in society and the world. At the same time, it is especially worth emphasizing the scientific nature of understanding those facts that until now have been of a philosophical nature. The scientific approach most clearly manifested itself in the understanding of culture as a semiotic system, which, on the one hand, concentrates in itself a certain amount of information useful to society, and on the other hand, appears as an instrument for obtaining this information and satisfying society itself with it.

Recently, the study of language in terms of its interaction with culture has become extremely relevant. Cultural linguistics is a new independent branch of linguistics that studies the characteristics of culture reflected in language. Language serves as a means of understanding culture and national mentality. In this regard, a specific feature of the manifestation of cultural linguistics knowledge is the consideration of a person from the point of view of his linguistic activity.

We know that cultural linguistics is the study of language, culture, and people a science that reflects and studies the characteristics of the language of culture. Linguistic analysis of linguistic units of linguistics and cultural community characteristic features, describes national-cultural characteristics, communicative category, explains the importance of the concept of national culture.

The main task of cultural linguistics studies is a certain study cultural origin of the communication space, discourse and language, as well as linguistic interpretation of terms of cultural signs of unity, historical memory of the people consists of description based on the prism.

Cultural linguistics as an independent direction took shape in the 90s of the 20th century. The term “cultural linguistics” appeared in connection with the works of the phraseological school headed by V.N. Telia. V.A. Maslova defines this direction as follows: “Cultural linguistics is a branch of linguistics that arose at the intersection of linguistics and cultural studies and studies manifestations of the culture of a people that are entrenched in the language”.

Every nation initially has different ways of understanding the world. This is connected with the spiritual culture, the way of thinking of a certain society, and language. It follows that every person, one way or another, considers himself to be a certain ethnic entity. The culture of each ethnic group consists of a complex set of knowledge. Customs, rituals, traditions, arts, crafts, social relations form culture. Language, in turn, is a way of penetrating into the modern

mentality of a nation, as well as into the worldview of people of long ago. Cultural linguistics focuses on a new system of cultural values put forward by new thinking, modern life of society, a complete, objective interpretation of facts and phenomena and information about various areas of the country's cultural life. This objective and holistic interpretation of the culture of the people requires from cultural linguistics a systematic representation of the culture of the people in their language, in their dialectical interaction and development, as well as the development of a conceptual series, which contributes to the formation of modern cultural thinking.

The main task of cultural linguistics is to reveal the mentality of the people and their culture through language. So, the material for the study of cultural phenomena is language in its living functioning in discourses of various types: in spoken language, in fiction, in political rhetoric. Recording information and entering it into collective memory occurs thanks to texts, because Human cultural exploration of the world occurs through the study of its language.

References:

1. Sharifian, Farzad (2011). Cultural Conceptualisations and Language: Theoretical Framework and Applications. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
2. Usmanova Sh. Lingvokulturologiya. – T.: 2014.
3. Газизов Р. А., Мурясов Р. З. Лингвокультурология и современная лексикография. 2016.. № 2
5. Маслова В.А. Лингвокультурология.–М.: 2001
6. Драч Г.В. Культурология – Ростов-на-Дону: Феникс, 2005.
7. Маслов Ю.С. Введение в языкознание. - М.: МГИМО, 1987.